

**ORGANO-ARSENICALS. PART III. SULPHANILAMIDO.
N¹-PHENYLARSONIC ACIDS***

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The action of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride on *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminophenylarsonic acids as well as on 4-amino-3-methylphenylarsonic acid has been studied.

p-Arsanilic acid is the parent substance of a number of therapeutically active organo-arsenicals. Since Ehrlich's discovery of the trypanocidal activity of atoxyl, a large number of organo-arsenicals have been synthesised and tested.

4-Phenylsulphonamidophenylarsonic acid [I, X=As(OH)₂] has been prepared from 4-phenylsulphonamido-aniline (I, X=NH₂) by Mouneyart's modification (Eng. Pat., 142947 of 1919) of Bart's method for replacing NH₂ group by AsO(OH)₂ group. Compound (I) has also been prepared by the condensation of benzene sulphonyl chloride with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of alkali or alkali carbonate (Mouneyart, F.P. 401586 of 1906).

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to preparing and making a systematic study of compounds having in their molecules a combination of arsonic acid and sulphonamido groups.

p-Acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride, when reacted with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium carbonate, N⁴-acetylsulphanilamido-N¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic acid (II) results. The reaction was tried under varying conditions *viz.*, (i) by dissolving the reactants in a solvent like alcohol, benzene or chloroform; (ii) in presence of alcoholic caustic soda; (iii) in presence of sodium ethylate, sodamide, dimethylaniline, pyridine, sodium carbonate and sodium bicarbonate; and (iv) by fusion of the two reactants. Of all these methods, the one using the sodium salt of the arsonic acid has been found to be successful.

The sodium and barium salts of (II) have been prepared. Compound (II) on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid yields sulphanilamido-N¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic acid (III, R=H₂).

* A note on this work appeared in *Science and Culture*, 1945-46 11, 505.

While its sodium and barium salts are quite stable, the potassium salt decomposes on keeping. Compound (III, R=H₂) has been condensed with benzaldehyde and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde to give *N*⁴-benzylidene-sulphanilamido-*N*¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic acid (III, R=CH.Ph) and *N*⁴-*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene-sulphanil-amido-*N*¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic acid [III, R=CH.C₆H₄.NMe₂ (*p*)] respectively. Although Northey (*Chem. Rev.*, 1940, 27, 99) has referred to compound (III, R=H₂) from personal communications, no details seem to have been published.

Attempts to isolate pure products from the condensation of *o*- and *m*-aminophenyl-arsonic acids with *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride were unsuccessful.

The action of 4-amino-3-methylphenylarsonic acid (Friend, 'Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry', Vol. XI, Part II, p. 224) with *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride gives the sodium salt of *N*⁴-acetylsulphanilamido-2'-methylphenyl-4'-arsonic acid (IV).

Its hydrolysed product could not be obtained in a pure form.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

*N*⁴-Acetylsulphanilamido-*N*¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic acid (II).—To a solution of the sodium salt of *p*-arsanilic acid (5.76 g.) in water (24 c.c.) containing anhydrous sodium carbonate (1.25 g.), *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride (5.6 g.) was gradually added under stirring. After complete dissolution, the liquid was filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. A white semi-solid separated out immediately. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and fresh hydrochloric acid added and allowed to stand for 3 hours. The resulting white powder was collected and purified by dissolution in dilute sodium hydroxide and precipitation with dilute hydrochloric acid, yield 5.8 g. (Found: As, 17.94, C₁₄H₁₅O₆N₂SA requires As, 18.11 per cent).

Sodium salt of (II).—Compound (II) was suspended in water and dilute sodium hydroxide solution added drop by drop with shaking till the whole of the substance went into solution. An equal volume of alcohol was then added and the liquid well stirred. The sodium salt first separated as an oil, which on standing changed into white powder. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. (Found: As, 17.03. C₁₄H₁₄O₆N₂SA₂Na requires As, 17.20 per cent).

Barium Salt of (II).—Similarly, the barium salt was prepared using a solution of barium hydroxide instead of sodium hydroxide. [Found: As, 15.36. (C₁₄H₁₄O₆N₂SA)₂Ba requires As, 15.57 per cent].

*Sulphanilamide-*N*¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic Acid (III, R=H₂)*.—The compound (II, 2 g.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (1:1, 10 c.c.) till all the solid went in solution and for a further period of 5 minutes. The liquid was then cooled, made alkaline with ammonia,

filtered and the filtrate acidified with acetic acid when the amino compound separated. It was filtered out, dissolved in alkali and reprecipitated with acetic acid; the product was soluble in hydrochloric acid. (Found: As, 20.0. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4N_2SAs$ requires As, 20.17 per cent).

Sodium salt of (III, R=H₂) was prepared by dissolving the acid in the requisite amount of aqueous sodium hydroxide and precipitating with alcohol. (Found: As, 18.81. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_2SAsNa$ requires As, 19.04 per cent).

Barium salt of (III, R=H₂) was prepared by dissolving the acid in the requisite quantity of aqueous barium hydroxide and precipitating with alcohol. [Found: As, 16.97. $(C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_2SAs)_2Ba$ requires As, 17.06 per cent].

N⁴-Benzylidene-sulphanilamido-N¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic Acid (III, R=CH.Ph).—Compound (III, R=H₂; 2 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.6 g.) were thoroughly mixed in a test-tube and heated in an oil-bath at 140–150° for 2 hours and then the mass was cooled, extracted with sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave a thick precipitate which was collected, washed with a small quantity of water and dried, yield 1.8 g. (Found: As, 16.15. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N_2SAs$ requires As, 16.30 per cent).

N⁴-p-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-sulphanilamido-N¹-phenyl-4'-arsonic Acid (III, R=CH.C₆H₄.NMe₂).—Compound (III, R=H₂; 3.5 g.) was thoroughly mixed with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.5 g.) and heated in a hard glass test tube in an oil-bath at 140–150° for 3 hours and then the dry mass was extracted with alkali and filtered. The filtrate on acidification deposited a precipitate which was collected, washed with water and dried, yield quantitative. (Found: As, 14.80. $C_{21}H_{22}O_3N_2SAs$ requires As, 14.91 per cent).

Sodium Salt of N⁴-Acetylsulphanilamido-2'-methylphenyl-4'-arsonic Acid (IV).—The sodium salt of 4-amino-3-methylphenylarsonic acid was prepared by dissolving the acid in hot sodium hydroxide solution (25%) and pouring the filtered solution into cold alcohol. The salt separating was collected, washed with alcohol and dried.

To a solution of this salt (2.5 g.) in water (10 c.c.) containing anhydrous sodium carbonate (1.1 g.) *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylchloride (2.3 g.) was added in small quantities with shaking. After the reaction was over, it was filtered and the filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid when the arsonic acid precipitated out. It was collected and converted into its sodium salt by dissolving in the requisite amount of alkali and precipitating with alcohol, yield 2.4 g. (Found: As, 16.49. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4N_2SAsNa$ requires As, 16.66 per cent).

The sulphanilamidophenylarsonic acids detailed in this paper are insoluble in common organic solvents, have no sharp melting points, and are purified only by repeated precipitation with acid from their solution in alkali.

Estimation of Arsenic.—The volumetric methods being easy to operate are suitable for routine analysis and hence these were critically studied. Ewin's method

(*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 1355) was found to give fairly reliable results with the present series of compounds. But the time required for the digestion of the compounds was very long and the considerable frothing, which happened during digestion, made the method rather cumbersome.

Das-Gupta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 95) dissolved the pentavalent arsonic acids in concentrated hydrochloric acid with warming and treated the solution with potassium iodide. The liberated iodine was then titrated against standard thiosulphate solution. This method could not, however, be applied for the present series of compounds as the end-point was not at all sharp.

The method developed by Robertson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 182) was used in the present investigation. The end-point was very sharp, the time taken was less than that obtained in other methods and the results were reliable.

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